

Analysis of the determinants of the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon

Analyse des déterminants de la promotion des énergies renouvelables au
Cameroun

Auteur 1 : NGUIFFO Joel Salomon

Auteur 2 : ETOA ETOA Jean Bosco

NGUIFFO Joël Salomon (doctoral student)
University of Yaoundé 2, Soa / Faculty of Economics and Management, Cameroon
nguiffoc3@gmail.com

Professor ETOA ETOA Jean Bosco (lecturer)
University of Yaoundé 2, Soa / Faculty of Economics and Management, Cameroon
jbetoa@gmail.com

Déclaration de divulgation : L'auteur n'a pas connaissance de quelconque financement qui pourrait affecter l'objectivité de cette étude.

Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : NGUIFFO.J S & ETOA ETOA.J B (2022) « Analyse des déterminants de la promotion des énergies renouvelables au Cameroun », Revue African Scientific Journal, Volume 3, Numéro 12, pp : 316-333.

Date de soumission : Avril 2022

Date de publication : Juin 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6824803

Copyright © 2022 – ASJ

ABSTRACT:

This article aims to analyze the main determinants of the promotion of renewable energies (RE) in Cameroon. To achieve this objective, we conducted an econometric study based on the VAR (Vector Autoregressive) model over the period 2002-2014. The empirical results show that the electric park, the level of CO₂ emissions due to the electricity sector, and the quality of institutions have a significant effect on the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon. On the other hand, the level of per capita income has no significant effect.

KEYWORDS: renewable energies (RE), promotion of RE, energy transition, VAR approach.

RESUME:

Cet article a pour objectif d'analyser les principaux déterminants de la promotion des énergies renouvelables (ENR) au Cameroun. Pour que cet objectif soit atteint, nous avons fait une étude économétrique en se basant sur le modèle VAR (Vectoriel Autorégressif) sur la période de 2002-2014. Les résultats empiriques montrent que le parc électrique, le niveau d'émission de CO₂ due au secteur électrique, et la qualité des institutions ont un effet significatif sur la promotion des énergies renouvelables au Cameroun. Par contre, le niveau de revenu par habitant n'a pas d'effet significatif.

MOTS-CLÉS: énergies renouvelables (ENR), promotion des ENR, transition énergétique, approche VAR.

Introduction:

Most human activities, especially those that contribute to socio-economic development, rely on energy. Thus, the development of a society is dependent on the satisfaction of certain basic needs such as: housing, leisure, health, transport, food, education, etc. Access to modern energy sources is essential for socio-economic development. Energy has several advantages for our economic society, but can also have certain disadvantages, especially when it is not renewable. Indeed, according to the report drawn up by the *Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century* (REN21, 2015a, p.27), world final energy consumption is dominated by energy of fossil origin (oil, natural gas and coal) by approximately 78.3% in 2013. Thus, energy demand is largely covered by fossil fuels, which are the main sources of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. According to IPCC ¹(2007), to mitigate the effects of climate change, it is necessary to stabilize the atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂). In addition to contributing to climate change, the use of fossil fuels causes air quality problems (acid rain, particles, etc.), disturbs groundwater and pollutes the oceans. There is no energy whose use is perfectly clean, even if the damage is of a different nature and extent from one energy to another. These environmental nuisances are all the more worrying as the quantities of energy consumed are large, Jancovici (2004). In view of all this, we can therefore ask ourselves the question of knowing what could be the factors for promoting renewable energies for sustainable development in Cameroon?

The main objective of this work is to analyze the factors likely to promote renewable energies in Cameroon, and to achieve this, we will first review the theoretical and empirical literature on the subject in question. In a second step, we will mobilize time series econometrics in order to be able to test the link between these different factors and the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon. In other words, in this research work, we will have literature review in the first part and in the second part, we will have the methodology and the discussion of the results.

¹IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

1. Literature review

We have made an overview of the econometric literature of the different factors likely to influence the promotion of renewable energies. We have grouped them into four categories: promotion policies, determinants related to the structure and dynamics of the energy sector, macroeconomic determinants and political determinants.

1.1. Public policies to promote renewable energies

The econometric literature on this subject is much more concerned with the effectiveness of policies in general but it is less so with the specific effectiveness of each instrument. These econometric studies also differ in terms of the method used to capture the influence of these policies.

Marques and Fuinhas (2012), conducted a study on a set of 27 countries in Europe over the period (1990-2007), which incorporates a broader scope of variables representing policies. The authors first constructed a variable that represents the number of policy measures in place in each country (*Accumulated Number of RE Policies and Measures*). Then, they tested the influence of different types of policies according to the general classification proposed by the “*Global Renewable Energy Policies and Measures Database*” of the IEA's: direct public investments, R&D grants, education and awareness policies, subsidies, regulatory instruments, voluntary agreements and tradable permits, and policy frameworks (strategic energy sector planning, renewable energy targets, etc.). The results confirm a positive and significant relationship in general of public policies on the level of investment in RE. However, with regard to the different policies, only subsidies and policy frameworks show a significant influence. On the other hand, regulatory instruments as well as other types of policies do not prove to be significant in the promotion of renewable energies according to this study.

Aguirre and Ibikunle (2014), in their study, chose an approach very similar to that of Marques and Fuinhas (2012). Their study covers a number of countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa), over the period from 1990 to 2010, we can also observe a negative relationship between tax incentive policies and the diffusion of renewable energies. One of the important limitations of these two studies is that they take into account all renewable energies in a global way, including biomass (in all its forms) and large hydroelectric power stations. Generally, these renewable energy sources are not taken into account in promotion policies, which can influence the results of the estimates (they can be biased).

Polzin et al. (2015), conducted a study to assess the different policies implemented in OECD countries over the period 2000-2011 using ordinary variables. In their study, the authors highlight the importance of a reliable policy framework with clear medium and long-term objectives. Their results show that fiscal and economic incentives (FIT, FIP) are the most relevant measures for investors thanks to a clear reduction in the risk associated with this type of project. Other indirect instruments, notably tradable emission permit systems, have a positive impact but only on the most mature technologies.

Cadoret and Padovano (2016), in their study, assessed two other policy variables. The first variable measures the level of commitment of each country (in %) for the contribution of renewable energies in the final energy consumption in the objectives for 2020 (according to 2009/28/EC Directive). The second variable is that of environmental taxes, which expresses the share of total revenue represented by environmental taxes, according to the Eurostat classification. Their results show a significant and positive effect for the first variable, but no statistically significant influence for the second variable. For the authors, this can be explained by the fact that the revenues from environmental taxes are not intended to protect the environment but are intended for budgetary purposes.

In his study, Nurcan (2016) uses data from the period 1990-2008 to analyze the effects of several policy instruments (feed-in tariffs, quotas, tenders and tax incentives) on the deployment of RE in Europe and the United States. They represent these instruments from “*dummy variables*”. The results show a positive influence of policies, but with different efficiencies depending on the type of instrument. The results also show that feed-in tariffs, tenders and tax incentives are effective mechanisms for stimulating RE deployment capacity, while the other commonly used policy instrument, the quota, is not. Finally, Kim and Park's (2016) work includes a single policy variable: ITDs. The results of the various models tested by this study show a positive and significant influence of TIFs.

1.2. Macroeconomic determinants

According to Del Río and Taracón (2012), the macroeconomic environment of a country is strongly correlated with the attraction of investments in the RE sector. Countries have at a certain period characteristics that make them more or less attractive for investments in general and for new technologies in particular. These characteristics include the existence of highly qualified workers, the quality of infrastructure, legal and financial security, among others.

1.2.1. The level of per capita income

Aguirre and Ibikunle (2014), Marques and Fuinhas (2012) and Chien and Hu (2008), in their work, integrated GDP per capita into their models. They made the basic assumption that countries with high income are more likely to promote renewables, because they can easily bear the costs of developing these technologies and encourage them through economic incentives.

1.2.2. Access to funding

One of the biggest obstacles to the deployment of RE is indeed the high initial investment cost (the problem of the payback time of the said investment and of the appropriate infrastructure). The energy sector, and in particular renewable energy, is more capital intensive than other industries because energy projects require a proportionally higher initial investment before production can begin (IFC, 2011). Another obstacle related to the deployment of these new technologies is the high information cost, in particular that associated with the search for data (Kim and Park, 2016). Moreover, unreliable or inaccurate information on the technical operation of various RE projects is a major source of uncertainty. Information imbalances between producers and investors / funders is also an element likely to hamper the dissemination process.

The study by Kim and Park (2016) examines the relationship between the development of financial markets and the diffusion of renewable energies from a panel of 30 countries for the period 2000-2013. The results claim that renewable energy growth is clearly faster in countries with well-developed financial markets, which is particularly true for energies that are more dependent on external financing such as solar. Thus, the influence of the financial markets on the promotion of renewable energies is then studied from two major sectors: the stock market (financing via the stock market) and the bank credit market. The results also show renewable energies are developing more rapidly in countries with well-developed financial markets and particularly for technologies dependent on external financing (financing outside the firm), in particular solar and wind power.

Pfeiffer and Mulder (2013), in their study examine, among other variables, the influence of certain financial factors on the development of renewable energies, distinguishing between domestic financing and international financing. They took as an approximate variable of the level of development of financial markets within each country, the ratio between total bank assets (deposits) and central bank assets, in order to highlight the importance of commercial

banks compared to central banks and indirectly the availability of credit. However, the results of their model show that this variable is not significantly influential. Concerning international funding, these authors tested the influence of official development assistance (ODA) on the level of dissemination of RE. They expected a positive influence from ODA given the fact that renewable energies represent one of the central axes of this type of transfer. First, ODA as measured in the study by Pfeiffer and Mulder (2013) includes all sectors and not just the renewable energy sector. Second, the share of ODA for the energy sector is mainly intended to finance off-grid power plants which are excluded from the dependent variable (due to lack of data).

1.3. Political determinants

Government policy is another factor that can potentially influence energy and environmental policies.

The studies of Potrafke (2010) and Biresselioglu and Karaibrahimoglu (2012), Neumayer (2003), show that political factors, such as the quality of governance, the influence of lobbies, and the political orientation of the governing parties are factors likely to influence both energy policy and environmental policy. However, these studies do not specifically show the role of political determinants on the diffusion of renewable energies. Cadoret and Padovano (2016) were the first to analyze the influence of purely political factors on the diffusion of renewable energies. In their work, these authors study in particular the share of renewable energies in final energy consumption using panel data from 26 European countries over the period 2004-2011. Firstly, to measure the influence of lobbies, they use as a proxy variable the value added of the industrial sector as a percentage of GDP, by testing the following hypothesis: a strong industrial sector is more inclined to resist the deployment of renewable energies because of their higher cost which affects the competitiveness of the industry. However, the correlation of this variable with the dependent variable (diffusion of RE) is low. Secondly, the quality of governance is measured by two indicators: the “*Corruption Perception Inde*” (CPI) of the NGO Transparency International and the “*Control of Corruption Index*” of the World Bank. The simple correlation between these two indicators and the variable to be explained is also weak. Thirdly, the influence of policy determinants is represented by a *dummy* variable that takes the value of one or zero depending on whether the governing coalition is center- right or left wing, according to data from the Inter-American Development Bank's *Database of Political Institutions* (DPI). The correlation

between this variable and the share of renewable energies varies according to the group of countries: in the EU-15 countries, left-wing governments seem to be more committed to the deployment of renewable energies, while the opposite is true in Eastern European countries.

1.4.Determinants related to the energy sector

1.4.1. The energy mix

The existing electricity supply in a country can condition the distribution of RE technologies in several ways. On the one hand, countries with a production mix strongly based on hydroelectricity and/or nuclear power may be less affected by the development of new low-carbon technologies Popp et al, (2011). Similarly, a generation of electricity highly concentrated on a particular source (for example nuclear) may reflect a situation of technological lock-in and the possible influence of a lobby from this industry which would try to keep its market share Pohl and Mulder, (2013). On the other hand, countries with a large number of hydroelectric power stations and dams have the storage capacity necessary to balance, at least in part, the intermittency of solar and wind power. From this point of view, renewable energies and large hydroelectric plants are complementary rather than competing technologies. The link between these sources of electricity generation is therefore difficult to predict.

1.4.2. The cost of conventional energy sources and the price of electricity

Renewable energies are in competition with other sources of electricity production. Thus, the availability of cheap fossil resources that can be used for the production of electricity, in particular gas and coal, can also condition the attractiveness of renewable energies. The higher the price of competing sources, the more attractive investments in RE will be, Popp et al. (2011). In the same line, several authors Del Río and Tarascon (2012) recall the importance of the price of electricity: the higher its price, the more investors will be encouraged to invest in renewable energies, all other things being equal. As such, Chang et al. (2009) for their part show a positive and significant relationship between energy prices and the contribution of renewables to energy supply in high economic growth regions, although this is not significant for low growth countries. As Popp et al. (2011) point out, it would be wise to include in the regression model the price of electricity generated by various sources in each country. However, the only data available are the overall electricity prices per country. This is clearly endogenous since it includes the price of electricity generated from RE. Instead, most models consulted include

proxy variables, including per capita gas and coal production and, if possible, the price of these sources in each country.

1.4.3. The degree of energy dependence

Some countries are net energy exporters while others are importers. Structural conditions, such as the availability of fossil resources in their territories and/or the existence of sufficient investments to exploit them, explain these opposite roles. In essence, countries dependent on external energy supply need to further develop local production sources based on renewable energy. Thus, reducing energy dependence is one of the main arguments in favor of RE development in both developed and developing economies Aguirre and Ibikunle, (2014). As Marques and Fuinhas (2012) point out, the expected theoretical relationship between these two variables is therefore positive: the more dependent a country is on external supply, the more incentive it will have to develop RE.

1.4.4. The level of energy-related GHG emissions

One of the fundamental reasons for promoting RE is to address climate change and reduce energy-related GHG emissions. Hence the need for a control variable that captures the relative importance of this issue in each country. Most works therefore include a variable representing CO₂ emissions (from the energy sector) per capita. Aguirre et al, (2014) recalls that environmental concerns stimulate investment in renewable energy, which is well known in the literature (see for example Sadorsky, 2009).

2. Methodology

Our study seeks to explain the factors likely to promote the diffusion of renewable energies for production, more specifically the level of promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon over a period of 13 years (2002-2014). With regard to the literature, different definitions of the variables can be proposed:

2.1.variable definition

2.1.1. Variable to be explained :

Electricity generation from renewable energy sources, in MW (RE): electricity generated from solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, small hydro, and does not take into account large hydro and thermal power plants. This approach was adopted by Aguirre and Ibikunle (2014). These authors advance two reasons justifying their choice; the first has to do with the fact that promotion policies

seek to achieve a target rate of RE contribution. The second is related to GHG mitigation policies, where the main goal for renewables is to increase their share, at the same time that fossil fuels decrease theirs. Thus, renewable energies must replace the most polluting options.

2.1.2. Explanatory variables:

Table 1. Description of variables

CODE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
<i>CO2</i>	<i>CO2 emissions related to energy production</i>	<i>World Bank</i>
<i>MIX</i>	<i>The share (%) of hydroelectricity and oil in electricity production</i>	<i>World Bank</i>
<i>GDP</i>	<i>GDP per capita (constant 2010 US\$)</i>	<i>World Bank</i>
<i>CORRUPT</i>	<i>Corruption perception index</i>	<i>World Bank</i>

Source: *Authors*

The structure of the electricity mix: The traditional technologies for electricity production can be grouped into three categories: hydro, nuclear and fossil fuels (coal, gas or oil based power plants). According to several authors (Pfeiffer and Mulder, 2013) the structure of the electricity fleet can influence investment decisions in RE either for political (lobby influence) or technical reasons. This variable captures the share of hydropower (large plant) and oil in the total electricity production in a year.

CO2 emissions from energy production in kt²: Countries with high levels of greenhouse gas emissions, especially carbon dioxide, need to develop clean energy sources, including RE, more rapidly. We therefore expect a positive relationship between the energy sector CO2 emissions per capita (CO2 emission) and the dependent variable.

GDP per capita (constant 2010 US \$): the basic assumption here is that the higher the income per capita in a country, the more likely it is to bear the costs of developing renewable energy technologies.

Corruption: This represents the quality of institutions. To measure it, we use the World Bank's corruption perception index, which is evaluated on a scale from 0 to 6 (low to high).

² KT : Kilotonne, unité de mesure d'énergie explosive équivalente à mille tonnes de TNT (trinitrotoluène)

Table 2.Descriptive statistics (from WDI World Bank data)

Variable	Obs	Average	Standard. Dev.	Minimum	Max
RE	17	10.83054	2.649258	7.576407	15.62279
MIX	15	-1.594363	4.914635	-17.98174	2.770705
CO2	14	149.5612	554.6217	-916.75	1257.781
GDP	15	.0749729	4.495083	-11.14348	12.59303
CORRUPT	16	.15625	.6428776	-.2	2.5

Source: Authors

2.2.Specification and choice of Model

Our model looks like this:

$$ENRE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MIX_{d1t} + \beta_2 CO2_{d1t} + \beta_3 PIB_{d1t} + \beta_4 CORRUP_{d1t} + \epsilon_t$$

2.2.1. Multicollinearity test

This is the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test and its inverse (1/VIF). For us to speak of the absence of multicollinearity, this statistic would have to be greater than 0.1.

Table 3. VIF test result

Variable	VIVID	1/VIV
GDP	3.69	0.271155
MIX	3.47	0.288224
CO2	2.51	0.398156
CORRUPT	1.09	0.918754
Mean VIF	2.69	

Source: Authors

We notice that the 1/VIF ratio is greater than 0.1 for all the coefficients, so we can conclude that there is no multicollinearity problem.

2.2.2. Unit root test

To measure the stationarity of our variables we will focus on two outcome values: $Z(t)$ and the Mackinon Critical Value. To say that a series is stationary, the $Z(t)$ must have a large negative number, and the p-value must be significant at 0.05 or 5 % level. If neither of these conditions is met, then we accept the null hypothesis, that is to say our series is not stationary. According to the table below, none of our variables were stationary at level, so we stationned in first difference according to the results below:

Table 4. Results of the ADF stationarity test

Variables	ADF		stationarity	
	T-stat	P-value	Yes/No	Integration order
<i>RE</i>	-3.565	0.0065	Yes	I(1)
<i>MIX_d1</i>	-3.264	0.0166	Yes	I(1)
<i>CO2_d1</i>	-4.208	0.0006	Yes	I(1)
<i>GDP_d1</i>	-5.942	0.0000	Yes	I(1)
<i>CORRUP_d1</i>	-4.119	0.0009	Yes	I(1)

Source: Authors

We notice that all our variables are stationary with probabilities below the threshold of 5%. The results of the ADF test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller) show that all our variables are stationary in first difference of order 1.

2.2.3. Cointegration Test

The Johansen cointegration test, also known as the eigenvalue test or the trace test, is a likelihood ratio test. There are two tests under Johansen cointegration: maximum eigenvalue test and trace test. For both test statistics, the original Johansen test is a test of the null hypothesis of no cointegration against the cointegration alternative. The results of our test are recorded in the table below:

Table 5. Result of the Johansen Cointegration test

Trend: constant number of obs : 13 Sample : 2002-2014 lags: 1					
Maximum rank	Parms	LL	eigenvalue	Trace statistics	5% critical
0	5	-208.5896	.	30.75	68.52
1	14	-171.6259	0.997	56.82	47.21
2	21	-154.2796	0.939	22.13	29.68
3	26	-148.1597	0.610	9.89	15.41
4	29	-144.0788	0.467	1.73	3.76
5	30	-143.214	0.124		

Source: Authors

It can be seen from this table that at rank zero, the trace statistic (30.7514) does not exceed the critical values (68.52). Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Furthermore, this suggests that our time series variables ENR, MIX, CO2, GDP and CORRUP are not cointegrated. Thus, since our variables are not cointegrated, we cannot use the **VECM (Vector Error Correction Model)**, but rather the **VAR (Vector Autoregressive Model)**

2.3.VAR model estimation

To estimate our equation we apply VAR modeling. The results of the analysis model estimates are as follows in the table below:

Table 6. Result of VAR model estimation

		Coef.	Stud.err.	z	p> z
RE					
	RE	.8917656	.2101904	4.24	0.000
	MIX	-.3435236	.15442	-2.22	0.026
	CO2	-.0009537	.0007151	3.13	0.002
	PIB	.0052451	.0809512	0.06	0.948
	CORRUP	-.4097415	.1947626	-2.10	0.035
_Cons	-2.41774	.810902	.810902	-2.98	0.003
Number of observations	13				
Log -likelihood	825.5663				
Nickname R²	0.981				
p >chi2	0.000				

Source: Authors

From the table below we observe that our model is globally significant according to the probability of chi2. From the results, we observe that the variable **MIX** (which represents the structure of the existing electric park composed mainly of large hydroelectric, thermal and oil power plants) has a negative and significant influence on the promotion of RE which joins the results of (Popp et al, 2011) which according to them, the countries having a production mix strongly based on hydroelectricity and/or nuclear may be less concerned by the development of the new low-carbon technologies.

Regarding the **CO2** variable (which represents the CO2 emission related to the energy sector) has a positive and significant influence on the promotion of RE, which confirms the results of Aguirre et al, (2014) who in their work show that environmental concerns stimulate investment in renewable energy.

Regarding the **GDP** variable, the results are in contradiction with the literature. We find that it is not significant but has a positive coefficient. Nevertheless this result confirms that of Carfora et al (2018) who in their study on a panel of 56 countries over a period from 2004 to 2011, showed that GDP does not affect the use of RE.

Finally, concerning the **CORRUP** variable, it has a significant and negative influence on the promotion of RE, which shows here the importance of the stability of institutions and governance mechanisms that ensure transparency and finally create a favorable environment for the development of RE.

2.4. Model Diagnosis

In order to verify the validity of the model, it is necessary to perform a number of tests.

2.4.1. Error autocorrelation test

2.4.2.

Table 7: Result of the Breusch - Godfrey test

lags(p)	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
1	0.192	1	0.6616

Source: Authors

According to the table above, the chi2 is greater than 0.05 or 5 %, the null hypothesis H0 is therefore accepted. In other words, there is no serial correlation between the residuals in our model.

2.4.2. Heteroscedasticity test

2.4.2.1. Breusch - Pagan heteroscedasticity test

Figure 1. Breusch - Pagan test result

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
 Ho: Constant variance
 Variables: fitted values of ENERE

chi2(1) = 1.50
 Prob > chi2 = 0.2205

Source: authors

According to our results, we found that (Prob= 0.2205) is therefore greater than 0.05, and therefore there is no heteroscedasticity.

2.4.2.2. White's heteroscedasticity test

Table 8. White's test result

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	14.00	13	0.3738
Skewness	0.75	4	0.9451
Kurtosis	1.21	1	0.2711
Total	15.96	18	0.5953

Source: Authors

In the same way as the Breusch-Pagan test, we found for White's that (Prob= 0.3738) and therefore greater than 0.05, and therefore there is no heteroscedasticity

2.4.3. Model stability test

Table 9. Model Stability Test Result

Eigenvalue	Modulus
.9430131	.943013
-.4052205 + .8053203i	.901523
-.4052205 - .8053203i	.901523
.6389738 + .4692705i	.792781
.6389738 - .4692705i	.792781
-.7211485	.721148
.1292259 + .6070545i	.620657
.1292259 - .6070545i	.620657

Source: Authors

The table above shows us that our model satisfies the stability conditions.

2.4.4. Normality test

Table 10. Result of model normality test

Variable	Skewness/Kurtosis tests for Normality				
	Obs	Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	joint Prob>chi2
r	13	0.9194	0.0906	3.41	0.1814

Source: Authors

Our table shows us that the probability Pr (Skewness) is 0.9194, which implies that the skewness is asymptotically normally distributed (skewness p-value > 0.05). Similarly, Pr (Kurtosis) indicates that kurtosis is also asymptotically distributed (p-value of kurtosis > 0.05). Finally, the chi (2) is 0.1814, which is greater than 0.05, implying its significance at the 5% level. The null hypothesis cannot therefore be rejected. Hence, according to Skewness' test for normality, the residuals show a normal distribution.

Conclusion:

This article aims to study the determinants of renewable energy promotion in Cameroon. In this context, we used VAR modeling for the period 2010-2017. From the results obtained, we were able to demonstrate that the electric park, the level of CO₂ emissions from the electric sector, and the quality of the institutions determine the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon. On the other hand, opening up the level of per capita income has no significant impact. Our results lead us to make the following recommendations: Improve the quality of our institutions and put in place governance mechanisms that ensure transparency in order to create a favorable environment for the development of RE. Limit the subsidies granted to fossil energies, including large hydraulic power plants, and to give more interest to renewable energies, also to set up an agency for the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon; whose main mission will be to define the policy for the promotion of renewable energies, such as: R&D subsidies, investment subsidies, production subsidies, green certificates, the competitive auction system, guaranteed feed-in tariffs, etc.

One avenue to explore in future research would be to model the effects of FDI and international trade on the promotion of renewable energies in Cameroon.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

- Aguirre, M., & Ibikunle, G. (2014). Determinants of renewable energy growth: A global sample analysis. *Energy Policy*, 69, 374-384.
- Biresselioglu and Karaibrahimoglu (2012), Government Orientation and the Use of Renewable Energy: The Case of Europe. *Renewable Energies, Elsevier*, vol. 47(C), pages 29-37.
- Cadoret, I., & Padovano, F. (2016). The political drivers of renewable energy policies. *Energy Economics*, 56, 261-269.
- Chang et al. (2009), Threshold effect of the rate of economic growth on the development of renewable energies based on a variation in the price of energy: Data from OECD countries. *EconPapers, Energy Policy*, 2009, vol. 37, issue 12, 5796-5802.
- Chien and Hu (2008), Renewable energy: An efficient mechanism to improve GDP. *Energy Policy, Volume 36, Issue 8, August 2008, p 3045-3052*.
- Del Río, P., & Tarancón, M.-Á. (2012a). analyzing the determinants of on-shore wind capacity additions in the EU: An econometric study. *Applied Energy*, 95, 12-21.
- Fuinhas (2012), 5802 are renewable energies effective in promoting growth? *EconPapers, Energy Policy*, 2012, vol. 46, volume C, 434-442.
- IPCC (2007), climate change 2007: synthesis report. Contribution of Working Group I, II and III to the fourth Assessment report of the intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, pp 104.
- Jancovici (2004), the greenhouse effect, are we going to change the climate? *Editions fields Flammarion 2004, (pages 217)*
- Kim, J., & Park, K. (2016). Financial development and deployment of renewable energy technologies. *Energy Economics*, 59, 238-250.
- Marks, AC, & Fuinhas, JA (2012). Are public policies towards renewables successful? Evidence from European countries. *Renewable Energy*, 44, 109-118.
- Nurcan (2016), The Evaluation of Renewable Energy Policies in EU Countries and US States: An Econometric Approach. <https://publons.com/publon/20661109/>
- Pfeiffer, B., & Mulder, P. (2013). Explaining the diffusion of renewable energy technology in developing countries. *Energy Economics*, 40, 285-296.
- Pohl and Mulder, (2013), Explaining the Diffusion of Renewable Energy Technologies in Developing Countries. GIGA Working Papers from the GIGA German Institute for Global and Area Studies, No 217.

Polzin, F., Migendt, M., Täube, FA, & von Flotow, P. (2015). Public policy influence on renewable energy investments. A panel data study across OECD countries. *Energy Policy*, 80, 98-111.

Popp, D., Hascic, I., & Medhi, N. (2011). Technology and the diffusion of renewable energy. *Energy Economics*, 33(4), 648-662.

Potrafke (2010), the political economy of electricity market liberalization: a transnational approach. *The Energy Journal*, p. 91-128 (38 pages)

Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century (REN21), (2015a). *Renewables 2015: Global Status Report*. Paris: REN21, available on: http://www.ren21.net/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/REN12-GSR2015_Onlinebook_low1.pdf (page consulted on May 19, 2015).

Sadorsky , (2009), Renewable Energy Consumption and Revenues in Emerging Economies, *EconPapers , Energy Policy*, 2009, vol. 37, issue 10, 4021-4028.